

Leading Change in a New Era of School Principals

By Dr. John T. Sherrill

There has been a changing of the guard in campus leadership. According to a study by RAND Corp, approximately 16% of administrators are leaving the profession. That number is higher, approximately 23% in the rural districts (Superville, 2023). New principals are assuming leadership roles and taking on-campus instructional leadership initiatives like never before. Becoming a principal in Texas requires candidates to hold a valid classroom certificate, have at least two years of creditable teaching service, complete an educator preparation program and pass a comprehensive exam that tests competency in skills related to school culture, executive leadership and human resources, among others (Texas Education Agency, 2023). With barriers to entry being what they are and new administrators at the helm, the task can seem quite daunting. Determining the best course of action can be formidable. For some, the answer may lie in Marzano's strategies for High Reliability Schools.

At the outset, I will tell you that I receive no compensation from Marzano Associates for this endorsement. As a practitioner taking over a school amid a pandemic, I sought strategies that would make my campus better. In fact, during my first faculty meeting, it was asked (virtually, of course) whether we would continue with HRS. I was so thankful the teacher asked that question because it gave me a chance to impart my philosophy of education to my new staff. I told the teacher, "We're going to do what is right by the kids. If that happens to line up with HRS, then so be it." To date, it has.

School Culture

When establishing cultural norms, it is important to set your sights on student success. With all the demands on educators and the persistent turnover in administration, it is imperative to set consistent instructional practices across all classrooms and staff (Desravines, Aquino, & Fenton, B, 2016, pp. 11-12). Establishing a leadership team is critical to the success of a new leader. Leadership teams can and should be comprised of administrators, lead teachers, campus/district directors and anyone that may affect change with the instructional staff of the campus. In "Leveraging Leadership 2.0," Bambrick-Santoyo states that these leaders need to be reliable and receptive to the implementation of best practices (2018, p. 292). With this in mind, our newly formed leadership team sought to build practices that would provide a sound culture for our faculty and students. As Marzano et al. would describe, "maintaining a safe and orderly environment is important, but it is not nearly enough. Every school leader must ensure a safe and orderly environment for both student and adult learning. But if school leaders seek to create excellent schools, they must move beyond running a tight ship (2018, p. 3)." As a high reliability school, it is imperative to constantly receive and review feedback from stakeholders. My school uses Google Forms for such a task because it is efficient and provides data our team can view in real-time. In "Leading a High Reliability School," Marzano et al. offers different components that are necessary to accurately predict student success, called "leading indicators." For the level one indicators (which

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revolve around safe, supportive and collaborative culture), the model identifies eight different leading indicators. Of those, principals can focus on high-yield strategies with the critical components. The critical component in the leading indicators revolving around safety and school culture is the professional learning community (2018, pp. 52-54). A professional learning community “offers a very powerful way of engaging teachers in reflecting upon and refining their practice. Securing improvements across large numbers of schools and classrooms...will not happen unless teachers are fully engaged in the change process and feel a high degree of ownership about the outcomes. (Harris & Jones, 2010, p. 174).” Our school sets norms and goals for their PLCs. We consistently monitor the goals and alter them when needed. The personal ownership and agency given to our teachers have helped them to buy into our campus PLC goals. The collaboration, both horizontally and vertically, has opened up conversations about remedial tactics, and information about instructional delivery and provided context across various teachers. Flanagan et al. (2016) (as cited in Marzano et al. (2018, p. 55)) note five commitments that leaders must make to lead PLC implementation: 1) understand what it means to be a PLC, 2) find the courage you need to lead, 3) build a climate of trust, 4) shape school structures for success and 5) create clarity in collaboration. As a part of this initiative, we had a leadership ambassador in each PLC team meeting. This gave our leadership team an opportunity to receive direct feedback that would be shared with our larger administrative team. Further, it allowed a teacher-leader to champion the cause with their peers.

Effective Teaching In Every Classroom

Savvy administrators who desire consistent results over a sustained period are wise to create an instruction framework. An instructional framework, or common classroom expectations, sets meaningful experiences for learnings across the campus. Grounded in the research from Marzano et al., school leaders should have a vision for the instructional leverage of the campus and know it when they see it (2018, p. 87). At our school, we have a living document that was created by a committee of teachers. We review our Common Classroom Expectations document with our staff and students. It is not an artifact of who we are. It is a compact between administration, teachers, students and stakeholders about the experiences that will persist in each classroom. Further, a meaningful framework that has been collaborated on with faculty has helped guide our professional development and PLCs agendas. Teachers seek to have a structure that focuses them on the mission and improves their professional practice (McAbee, 2022). By collaborating on and implementing an instructional framework document, our new and seasoned principals can help build buy-in and create structure.

Instructional Rounds

There is an adage, “inspect what you expect.” That is true in administration, too. After you have set your document for effective teaching in every classroom (High Reliability Schools - Leading Indicator 2.1), it is important to build a platform where teachers can observe and discuss effective

tive teaching (Marzano et al., 2018, pp. 100-103). At my school, we implement instructional rounds (IR). Instructional rounds are a time when colleagues go into a teacher's class, observe for about 10-12 minutes and provide positive feedback. We use our common classroom expectations document as a checklist. The IR team will create notes on the document of positive events occurring in the classroom. They will then debrief and discuss best practices and what that may look like in their teaching. When the team finishes, they submit the artifacts to the office, where we scan them and email them to the observed teacher to provide feedback. It is important to note that these are not formal observations; rather, they are data points for best practices that lead to student success. Additionally, we give the observed teacher an opportunity to give feedback via a Google survey. This completes the loop and lets the teacher provide input on the overall process. This process has been valuable for our teachers and students. At first, teachers were skittish, and students would stiffen up when the team entered the room. Nowadays, it is second nature. This process and the discourse that follows allow our administrators, teachers and colleagues to focus on best practices and reflect on insights garnered (Hatch & Roegman, 2012). For us, this has been gold!

Celebrate the Wins

One final thought I would share with new principals or those seeking to affect change would be to celebrate the wins. In our school, we fostered the notion of student success. Common classroom expectations is the tool we use for that. We reference this document in our professional development, PLCs, instructional rounds and faculty meetings. It is on prominent display in our hallways and our classrooms. Our faculty and staff see it daily. So do our students. Therefore, before our monthly staff meetings, I consult our students (again through Google Forms) and ask about one of our core components. For example, one of our common expectations is *recognize and reinforce*. So, I will ask the students which teachers do a great job of this and what that means to them. These responses are compiled and shared with the entire staff and faculty at the faculty meetings. The staff cheers and joins in on the accolades as they come up throughout the faculty meeting. If you are unsure of how to build buy-in on your campus, recognize your good teachers. Allow them to be the proponents of growth and change. If you want to take it to the next level, give the students a voice in recognizing their teachers.

Conclusion

The literature supports campus administrators' efforts to improve school culture, build agency in their teachers and leaders, and recognize the efforts of their personnel. Although these changes will be met with implementation dips and some resistance, it is critical to build collegial relationships (Bostick, 2021) that will empower healthy dialogue, vulnerability, and persistent coaching and growth over time. At our school, we were fortunate to have an overall understanding of the High Reliability Schools framework. The best practices and continual growth modeled in HRS have given us a guide to navigating student success.

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